

Administration Of Justice And Kindness By David (2 Samuel 9:1-12): Lesson For Nigerian Leaders

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ABSTRACT

One of the virtues that is sacrosanct to the development and progress of any society is good justice. This is an act that deals with giving to every individual his/her right without bias. A look at the Bible and the teaching of Christ revealed that justice is one of the concepts that is emphasized for love, unity, peace and progress of the society. Apart from this, the teachings of Prophet Isaiah, Amos and Hosea among others revolve around good justice. In Nigeria, there is a judiciary system which upholds justice in the constitution of the country and it is expected that both leaders and followers should uphold it. But the problem in Nigeria society is that there is no true justice from some of our leaders or those at the position of authorities. It could be inferred that some leaders are oppressing their subordinates which implies that there is no fair treatment among the citizenry. It is on this note that this study examined the attitude of David towards Saul's family in the area of administering good justice and the lesson which can be drawn from it for the use of Nigerian leaders and the generality of the populace in the nation. The study adopted historical method with a means of collecting materials from the Bible, textbooks, journals, magazines among others. The findings of the study revealed that the scripture emphasized justice among the Israelites, Amos as a prophet preached against injustice among Israelites in the Bible. Not only this, the work revealed that there can be good harmonious relationship where justice is well administered, it was also noted that perversion of justice is rampant in Nigerian society. The work therefore recommended that it is good if Nigerian leaders can emulate David in the Bible in his attitude towards Saul's family. Leaders and individuals should shun covetousness, pride and embrace the fear of God. Leaders should endeavor to keep their promises especially with the electorates and people at the helms of affair should use their position to help people rather than for oppression.

Keywords: Administrations, Justice, Kindness, Society and Leaders

INTRODUCTION

One of the most contended issues in the Bible apart from God's judgment and reality of heaven and hell fire is good justice. In the scripture, Prophet Amos stressed the need for good justice and how it affected the society. Justice is a concept that deals with the treatment of people in a fair and morally way. It is a means or legal process of judging and punishing people for an act been committed (Michael, 820). In any given society, issue relating to interpersonal relationship of man remains sacrosanct. However, when people had the opportunity to occupy a particular position which eventually brings about relationship, some use the position as a weapon of revenge, a means to enrich themselves, enslave and torture the people under their jurisdiction. Whereas others see the position as God-given opportunity; the position is used to promote justice and show kindness to people around them. In Nigerian society, there is high level of oppression, corruption and perversion of justice, as we have among the Israelites in the Bible.

Right from the scripture, God sets out law and standards for His people, the laws are meant to govern their relationship with Him (God) and their fellow humankind. Among other things which the law of God consists is warning against the perversion of justice. In Nigeria, there is a constitution which governs the interpersonal relationship of people and the government, which people tagged as the hope of the common man. Besides, the society we live in is characterized by all kinds of vices like oppression, bribery, unfairness, favoritism among others. Meanwhile, the poor ones are oppressed and cheated, but the irony aspect is that some of these people cannot go to court of law because they do not have the grace to engage the service of a legal practitioner; at times, those who do so do not get fair judgment. (Anayochukwu, 18) while quoting the word of Farida chairman, Economics Financial Crimes Commission in 2010 opined that: most of the people that are politically exposed are also more financially exposed and command heavier war chest than those without political background. She added that with their resources, they can employ the best of lawyers and complicate the entire prosecution process. To this end, issues relating to fairness and justice have reduced to a certain extent in Nigerian society. It is on this that this work examined David's administration of justice and kindness to the household of Saul and the lessons which Nigerian leaders can gain from it for the growth of Nigerian society.

Who was David?

David was one of Jesse's children; as the youngest child, he was the keeper of his father's sheep. In his work, he demonstrated the spirit of courage, humility and faithfulness by killing both lion and bear that tried to attack the flock of His father. As a child, he displayed an outstanding musical talent with the harp, a talent which led him to King Saul's palace (Youngblood, 332). Besides, David was known to be second king of Israel after Saul. He established a united kingdom over all Israel with Jerusalem as its capital. He was also known to be armor-bearer to King Saul (1 Samuel 16:21). David is seen in the scripture as an intimate friend to Saul's son Jonathan.

While under Saul, David demonstrated his talent and ability. In 1 Samuel 17:50, it was recorded that David killed Goliath, a Philistine giant who led a war with the Israelites. His popularity after the killing of Goliath brought Saul's envy and wrath to the extent that Saul's fear increased until he could no longer hide his desire to eliminate David's life, this made David to flee from Saul's pursuit. Meanwhile, in the course of searching for the life of David, David on two occasions spared the life of the King because he regarded him as God's anointed man. David later became King of Israel after the death of King Saul and his sons at Gilboa. (Johannes, 237) states that, David had a prosperous reign of forty (40) years and he could be seen as a prototype of the Messiah through whom God mediated his blessing to Israel.

Relationship of David with King Saul

The rejection of King Saul came after his disobedience to the words of God. In 1 Samuel 13:4-15, when Israelites were about to fight the Philistines, the custom and habit of the people is to perform sacrifice before going for any war. But it could be inferred that Samuel who was the priest and the person to perform the sacrifice was delayed in coming. This made Saul to go ahead to performed the sacrifice contrary to the law of God. When Samuel came and saw what Saul did, he was not happy thereby pronounced the non-continuation of Saul's throne for he was accused of usurping the function of the priesthood (Ojo and Ojebode, 74-75). This implies that the action of Saul could be interpreted as an act of disobedience to the commandment of Yahweh. As a corollary, 1 Samuel 13:13 acknowledges that Saul have done foolishly and have not kept to the commandment of God, which He (God) commanded him.

Apart from this, in 1 Samuel 15, Saul was instructed by God through his priest (Samuel) to destroy the Amalekites for opposing Israel on her way to Canaan from Egypt. The fight should be seen as a holy war in which the enemy must be totally destroyed. But at the end of the day, Saul and his people did contrary to the word of God by sparing the life of the King and picked some valuable items from the battle field as against the instruction of God. It was at this point that the total rejection of Saul was made as the King of Israel.

Meanwhile, at the point of rejection of Saul as king, the scripture recorded that he suffered from mental depression thereby need the service of a musician who will be making him happy. Thus, a man who had already been anointed secretly as King after Saul by Samuel was suggested by Saul's servants as a man who was skillful in playing the lyre for King Saul. After much inquiry, a son of Jesse the Bethlehemite, who was skillful in playing, a man of valor, a man of war, very prudent in speech and a man of good presence was presented to King Saul (1 Samuel 16:18). It could be inferred that the request and agreement between King Saul and David's father was reached. At the initial stage, Saul as a King loved David greatly and made him his armor-bearer.

As said earlier in this work, David came to the house of Saul because of the evil spirit from God that came upon him for doing contrary to the will of God. However, instead of love that supposed to exist between the King and his servant, it was later realized that issues relating to envy, hatred and jealousy started emanating in the behaviour of King Saul towards David. Apart from evil spirit from God that came upon Saul, he noticed that the name and fame of David have become more popular than his own after the killing of Goliath. Besides, he also realized that David had a close relationship with Jonathan his son and Michal his daughter which he did not like. He thought that through such relationship David will have more knowledge about his family which he considered to be dangerous for him and his family. Apart from this, Saul suspected that there is every tendency that the popularity of David might lead to wresting the kingdom from him and from Jonathan (Dickson, 49). The scenario above later led to searching for the life of David, but the fact that Jonathan loved David, the action and attitude of his father did not keep him away from David. Instead, he revealed most of the secret ways which his father have to eliminate the life of David.

Administration of Justice and Kindness by David: Lesson for Nigerian Leaders

For the growth and development of a society or nation, issues relating to good justice, kindness, equity are very sacrosanct. Justice according to Ayantayo 84 is a way of giving to every individual his/her right. It is also a means of doing away with act of injustice but promote justice and truth among one another. Ayantayo acknowledges that it is a concept that deals with liberty, freedom, equality and fair play if it is well administered. (Dzurgba, 39) corroborates the above view when he opined that justice is an act of responding to the need of other person in the society. He is of the view that the need could vary, since the need of the people are of various categories. (Omoregbe, 112) in the course of defining justice cited the word of St. Thomas Aquinas as the process and constant will to give each one his right/due. This states that justice involves act of fundamental right which should be treated as equals. In addition, if equal treatment is not given to the right of people in the society such could be termed as injustice.

Meanwhile, after the death of Saul, David became King in Israel and Judah. At this period, he lamented at the death of King Saul and his friend Jonathan. Besides, he demonstrated good justice and showed kindness to the family of Jonathan. As a God-fearing person, he makes a plea to keep to the promised of loyalty and kindness with Jonathan family. When Jonathan died, David did not forget the sacred love between him and his friend. However, to keep his promise, he asked if there is anybody he could show loyalty and kindness to, in order to fulfill the promise between him and his friend. It was at this period Mephibosheth, son of Jonathan was brought to him with the assistance of Ziba, a servant of Saul's family. David gave an assurance to the man that he will restore to him all the land that belonged to his grandfather and will be eating always at his table, indicating that he will be caring for him (1 Samuel 9:7). A look at the attitude of David in the Bible revealed that he demonstrated an act of justice to the family of Saul including his friend even after their deaths. He gave out what is meant for them; he was not selfish nor stood on what does not belong to him. As a way of comparism between the acts of justice being demonstrated by David and Nigerian leaders, it could be inferred that some cases in Nigeria remain a thing of concern going by the way such issues were handled. For instance the killing of Dele Giwa on 19 October, 1986 with a mail bomb, the annulment of June 12 election in 1993, the killing of Attorney General of the federation Chief Bola Ige on December 23, 2001, the abduction of the Chibok girls and many others reflect the act of injustice because the government was unable to provide solution to the problem or brought to book those who are behind the problems. In addition, most of these problems to a

certain extent have led to chaos and confusion in the society. The most unfortunate thing in Nigeria is that the government who cannot uphold good justice, how easy will it be for such government to show kindness to the families these people left behind? To bring about development, progress, peace, unity, equity in the country it is good if Nigerian leaders can make use of an idea of David in course of administering justice to the family of Saul. Thus, the following lesson can be drawn from David action.

One of the lessons that can be drawn from David attitude is Loyalty. David and Jonathan were friends before his death. 2 Samuel 20:17 revealed that Jonathan swore to love David much as himself. However, when Jonathan died, David's action could be seen as exemplary one by summoning Jonathan's son, Mephibosheth. His motive toward the man was wholly good, he kept to the promise between him and Jonathan. This is against some leaders in Nigeria situation who derive pleasure in oppressing others. Some do not bother about their previous relationship with acquaintances. Some even use their office to take revenge without minding the consequences. As a rider, some politicians in Nigeria do not bother about their promise during the electioneering campaign to the electorates instead of providing a conducive environment for people to live, they always add to their problem to make life more difficult for them, which is not a good virtue for the growth of the nation.

Another lesson that can be drawn from David's attitude is that he shunned the act of covetousness. A look at the scripture states that King David is one of the few Kings who executed justice and kindness to the people. Mephibosheth was summoned but when he got to the king and heard the words of assurance of daily provision and restoration, he bowed for the king. It was at this time the king announced to Ziba the restoration to Mephibosheth all that belonged to Saul and his family such as his fifteen sons and twenty servants to farm the land and bring in the crops for Mephibosheth's benefit (2 Samuel 9:9). 2 Samuel 9:10 started that David kept his promise to Jonathan's son for he ate on David's table like one of the king's son and all members of Ziba's family remained as servants to Mephibosheth in Jerusalem. Unlike Nigerian society when some of our leaders are not willing to declare their assets not to talk of giving out what is not meant for them. It is good if Nigerian leaders could shun covetousness and look for ways to use the resources in the nation for its growth. There are lot of natural and mineral resources in the nation that can be used to enrich the people, but it seems that most of the benefits from the resources are used for the selfish end of some leaders. This work reiterates that leaders need not to be covetous but look for a way to develop the nation.

David as a leader and King feared God: The Bible states that David administered justice to those who did not deserve it, this is because the death of Saul and his son Jonathan would have been an opportunity for him to inherit all their properties, yet he made it possible for Jonathan's son to enjoy the rights and privileges of his father. The action of David is in line with Proverbs 29:2 which stated that when God-fearing people are in position of authority, some benefits like fairness, equity, peace, love and progress in the society are promoted. In Nigerian society, some of our leaders are not with the fear of God; some are selfish, greedy and are not ready to assist people. Some are ready to hold on to lie, they pervert justice and punish people because they lack the fear of God. (Adesupo, 181) corroborates this view when he stated that a leader with fear of God will be committed to the nation's welfare, such leader will be patriotic to the development of the nation and hence have the interest of his subjects in mind. But the irony part of Nigerian society is that some of our leaders do not possess this trait which David as a leader exhibited. A good leader needs to uphold the fear of God before he/she could achieve.

One other lesson that can be drawn from David's attitude is that a leader should know that whatever position someone occupies is a privilege from God. Thus, leader are expected to use their stewardship of influence to promote love, peace, unity and justice among the people. (Omosuyi, 193) is of the view that responsible leadership entails good stewardship. He acknowledged that Nigerians have cited poor leadership and improper accountability which serves as one Nigerian's afflictions. David as a leader used his office to promote his people, a trait which is not commonly exhibited among Nigerian leaders. It is good if Nigerian leaders could be committed to the progress of the nation and promote the spirit of patriotism to develop.

Furthermore, there are other qualities which can be drawn from the attitude of David in administering justice to the household of Saul. Such include honesty and integrity, commitment, responsibility and accountability, spirit of reconciliation, fairness, empathy, hard work among others. All these traits assisted David to have a successful reign. For the growth and progress of the nation, it is good if Nigerian leaders imbibe some of these traits for peace and unity of the nation.

CONCLUSION

Based on the submission of this work, it could be inferred that issues relating to good justice have been an important thing in the society. It is a trait that promotes fairness, equity and equality of individual in the society. It is also significant because it promotes equal economic, educational and workplace opportunities. If well administered, it promotes and develops health sector and basic needs. In the Bible, David demonstrated the trait of equity and fairness to a family which is worthy of emulation not only by Nigerian leaders but to every individual. In Nigeria, there are lots of areas which Nigerian leaders need to show fairness and kindness for the purpose of peace and harmonious relationship. These include judiciary, education, health sector, social amenities among others. Besides, a look at Nigeria as a nation revealed that the country is blessed with many resources but the irony of it is that the citizens are suffering. Many are living under abject poverty, the security of the nation is not good, and there is high inflation of goods and services in the society. As a ruler, there is perversion of justice in the court of law, corruption prevail in all sectors as we have among the Israelite in the Bible. To allow peace, unity, progress and development in the society, it is good if Nigerian leaders can emulate some characters in the Bible who administered justice and show kindness to their people such as David, Joseph and Nehemiah who even defended the course of justice and progress of their nation.

Suggestions

To promote good justice, unity, peace and progress of the society the following suggestions are considered useful:

- (a) Nigerian leaders are advised to keep to their promises to the populace, for this will bring the sense of trust, confidence between the leaders and the followers and this will eventually bring unity, progress in the society. David as a leader exhibited this trait and was able to receive the favour of God.
- (b) To allow progress, unity, oneness in the society, leader(s) should shun the act of covetousness. If this can be done by the leaders there will be comfort on the part of the followers. Besides, unity, peace and development will reign in the society and life will not be difficult for people.
- (c) Before good justice can reign in any society, it is good for both leaders and followers to embrace the fear of God. If the fear of God is in the mind of people in the society, it will be easy for the leaders to share resources on equal basis and there will be reduction on corruption and perversion of justice among others in the society.
- (d) Another point of interest is that whoever is in the position of authority should have regard for other people, no matter their backgrounds or physical disabilities. Not minding the physical disability of Mephibosheth, David response to him was good, he did not neglect him, he gave out what is meant for him. Nigerian leaders should learn from this. It is not good for leaders to shun/neglect people but look for means to embrace them and provide for their need.
- (e) Be it a leader or follower, we should use our position to help people and not to oppress them. David had the opportunity to oppress the family of Saul but failed to oppress them instead, he sought for unity, administered justice and showed kindness to Saul's grandson even after the death of his father. It is good if leaders in Nigeria can borrow this idea for the peace of the nation.

WORKS CITED

Adesupo, P. A. An appraisal of Joseph as an economic reformer in Egypt: Lesson for Nigeria leaders in D. A. Falade, O. Olanusi, D. Z. Olupayimo & J. S. Ojewumi (Eds.), *Perspectives on Nigeria's Economic Environment*. Ibadan: Master Print Publishers. (2018): 181.

- Adesupo, P. A. Religious education and it moral virtues towards a sustainable development in Nigeria. Paper presented at 2021 School of Arts and Social Sciences conferences between 9 and 13 August, 2021 at Federal College of Education, Abeokuta.
- Anayochukwu, A. "We are eager to jail any corrupt Nigerian". *Tell*, June 28. How the courts Abet Corruption, (2010):18.
- Ayantayo, J. K. *Fundamental of Religious Ethics*. Ibadan: Samprints and Graphic.co. (2017):84.
- Dickson, K. A. *The history and religion of Israel. From Samuel to the fall of the Northern Kingdom*. London: Darton, Longman & Todd Ltd. (1981):49.
- Dzurgba, A. *Contemporary Ethics Theory on Issues*. Ibadan: John Archers. (2007):39.
- Holy Bible Revised Standard Version.
- Johannes, P. S. *Encyclopedia of World Religions*. New York: Concord Publishing foreign media Books. (2006): 237.
- Michael, R. *Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners*. United Kingdom: Macmillan Publishers. (2007): 820.
- Ojo, E. G. and Ojebode, P. A. *History and religion of Israel*. Lagos: Nathy Publishers. (2010): 74-75.
- Omoregbe, J. 1. *Ethics a systematic and historical study*. Lagos: Joja Educational Research and Publisher Ltd. (2000):112.
- Omosuyi, O. B. and Akinfisoye, E. O. Leadership and Accountability. A panacea to sustainable development in Nigeria. In D. A. Falade, O. B. Olanusi, A. T. Adelakun & J. S. Ojewumi (Eds.), *Nigerian leaders and accountability. A multidimensional perspective*. Ibadan: Masterprint publishers. (2020): 193.
- Youngblood R. F. *Nelson's New Illustrated Bible Dictionary*. Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers. (1995): 332.